

THE GREEN LEAN-AGILE MANAGEMENT (GLAM) FRAMEWORK FOR LONG-TERM OPERATIONAL EXCELLENCE: EMPIRICAL VALIDATION IN THE RIAU PALM OIL INDUSTRY

OKTA KARNELI¹, PAZLI², SURYALENA³, FRINI KARINA ANDIN⁴,
FEBRINA RITA ALBETA⁵ and ACHMAD FAJRI FEBRIAN⁶

^{1,2,3,4,5}Faculty of Social and Political Science, Universitas Riau, Indonesia.

⁶Faculty of Social and Political Science, Universitas Padjadjaran, Indonesia.

Email: ¹okta.karneli@lecturer.unri.ac.id, ORCID: ¹0000-0002-4686-2760, ²0000-0002-7843-3274,

³0000-0001-9185-2927, ⁴0000-0001-8635-7147, ⁵0009-0009-1799-0905, ⁶0000-0002-3039-7876

Abstract

Efforts to achieve long-term operational excellence in the crude palm oil (CPO) industry require a management approach that integrates efficiency, environmental responsibility, and adaptive capability. This research introduces and empirically assesses the Green Lean-Agile Management (GLAM) framework as a comprehensive model designed to enhance Sustainable Operational Excellence (SOE) in the palm oil sector of Riau Province, Indonesia. Anchored in the Natural Resource-Based View (NRBV) and Dynamic Capabilities Theory, the research examined the interdependencies among lean management practices, eco-innovation, and organizational agility in driving Long-Term Operational Excellence within a resource-intensive and environmentally regulated sector. We used a mixed-method design, combining PLS-SEM analysis of survey data from 205 mill managers and cooperative partners with qualitative triangulation through in-depth interviews and NVivo-assisted coding. The measurement model, comprising 39 reflective indicators, demonstrated strong reliability and validity. The results revealed that Lean Management significantly promotes Eco-Innovation, supporting the proposition that operational efficiency strengthens innovation capability. Eco-Innovation also enhances Organizational Agility and Long-Term Operational Excellence, confirming its mediating role within the GLAM framework. However, Organizational Agility shows no significant effect on Long-Term Operational Excellence, indicating limited strategic relevance in industries with long processing cycles and stable market dynamics. The research underscores the importance of green technology adoption, regulatory compliance, and cooperative partnerships to institutionalize GLAM practices and elevate sustainability performance across the CPO supply chain.

Keywords: Green Lean-Agile Management, Eco-Innovation, Organizational Agility, Long-Term Operational Excellence, PLS-SEM, Palm Oil Industry.

INTRODUCTION

The sustainability of the palm oil industry is not solely supported by the performance of processing mills but also heavily relies on the pivotal role of smallholders as key actors within the industrial ecosystem. In facing global market pressures, stringent environmental regulations, and fluctuating commodity prices, smallholders are increasingly required to enhance efficiency, adopt environmentally friendly practices, and demonstrate adaptive capacity in response to change. The Natural Resource-Based View (NRBV) theory posits that competitive advantage can be achieved through sustainable resource management, particularly by fostering environmentally oriented innovation among both palm oil industries and smallholders [2].

The Indonesian palm oil industry plays a strategic role in the national economy, contributing more than 50% of the global supply [1], with plantation areas expanding from 14.43 million hectares in 2018 to an estimated 16.83 million hectares by 2025 [3]. As one of the leading producers, Riau Province faces multifaceted challenges in maintaining operational excellence while complying with increasingly stringent environmental standards [4,5]. Global pressure for sustainable practices, commodity price volatility, and demands for operational efficiency require an integrated and comprehensive management approach [6,7,8,9,10].

According to data from the Badan Pusat Statistik (BPS) of Riau Province [4], there are 285 palm oil mills (POMs) operating under various partnership models, including Kredit Koperasi Primer Anggota (KKPA) schemes and independent smallholders. However, the implementation of operational excellence initiatives often lacks sustainability due to limited integration of environmental, social, and economic dimensions [21]. Preliminary studies have identified several critical issues, including inefficiencies in production processes, slow adoption of green technologies, and limited organizational responsiveness to market volatility [11,12,13,14,15].

This article proposes an integrative framework that combines the principles of Lean Management, Eco-Innovation, and Organizational Agility to ensure the long-term sustainability of operational excellence initiatives. The framework is grounded in the NRBV, emphasizing that sustainable competitive advantage can be attained through efficient and innovative resource management [16]. The integration of these three elements is expected to provide a holistic solution to the operational and environmental challenges currently faced by the palm oil industry in Riau. This article aims to address this research gap by proposing an integrative model that places both palm oil industries and smallholders at the center of analysis through three key elements, such as Lean Management, Eco-Innovation, and Organizational Agility. By analyzing data from two distinct partnership models in Riau Province, this article not only elucidates the theoretical relationships among these variables but also provides a practical framework for understanding how smallholders can directly contribute to achieving Long-Term Operational Excellence.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Long-Term Operational Excellence or Sustainable Operational Excellence (SOE) is defined as the organization's ability to achieve and sustain superior operational performance by integrating economic, environmental, and social dimensions in a balanced and continuous manner [17,18]. This concept evolves from the traditional understanding of operational excellence by embedding sustainability as a core component of long-term value creation. In the palm oil industry, SOE involves optimizing production efficiency, minimizing environmental impacts, and empowering local communities [19]. Attaining SOE requires not only process efficiency but also a transformation in organizational mindset, in which environmental stewardship and social responsibility are considered strategic imperatives rather than compliance obligations. Through this perspective, SOE represents both a performance philosophy and a dynamic capability that enables palm oil organizations to maintain competitiveness while aligning with global sustainability standards.

Lean Management serves as a foundational approach to achieving SOE, emphasizing the systematic elimination of waste and the enhancement of value across all operational processes [32]. Originating from the Toyota Production System, lean management seeks to maximize customer value while minimizing resource utilization and inefficiencies. Within the palm oil sector, lean principles translate into efforts to optimize production flow, improve machinery efficiency, and reduce processing losses [33]. Empirical evidence indicates that implementing lean practices can increase productivity by up to 30% while simultaneously reducing environmental footprints through improved resource management [26]. Moreover, lean implementation cultivates a culture of continuous improvement, employee involvement, and problem-solving, which are vital for sustaining operational excellence in a competitive and resource-dependent industry [34,35,36,37,38,39].

Complementing lean practices, Eco-Innovation focuses on developing and implementing new products, processes, and business practices that promote environmental sustainability while driving economic benefits [27,28]. In the palm oil industry, eco-innovation manifests through waste-to-energy initiatives, biogas capture systems, renewable energy adoption, and sustainable agricultural practices [29]. These initiatives contribute not only to pollution reduction and energy efficiency but also to cost savings and enhanced market reputation. Previous studies highlight that eco-innovation strengthens environmental performance while simultaneously reinforcing competitive advantage [30]. Aligned with the Natural Resource-Based View (NRBV), eco-innovation is conceptualized as a strategic capability through which firms transform environmental challenges into opportunities for sustainable growth [40,41,42,43]. Another key determinant of SOE is Organizational Agility, which refers to an organization's ability to sense and respond swiftly and effectively to environmental changes [23,24]. In the highly volatile palm oil industry, characterized by fluctuating prices, evolving regulations, and climate-related uncertainties, agility becomes an essential capability for maintaining performance stability and competitiveness [25]. Agile organizations exhibit flexible structures, rapid decision-making, and adaptive learning mechanisms that allow them to respond proactively to emerging challenges. However, applying agility in industries with long production cycles such as palm oil remains complex, as it requires balancing operational consistency with strategic responsiveness. Developing such agility demands not only internal flexibility but also collaboration with smallholders and supply-chain actors to strengthen collective responsiveness across the production ecosystem [44,45,46,47,48].

Drawing upon the integration of Resource-Based View (RBV) [16], Dynamic Capabilities Theory [22], and the Natural Resource-Based View (NRBV), this article constructs a comprehensive framework linking Lean Management, Eco-Innovation, Organizational Agility, and Sustainable Operational Excellence. The RBV emphasizes that valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable resources serve as the foundation of sustained competitive advantage. Dynamic Capabilities Theory extends this view by highlighting the firm's ability to integrate, build, and reconfigure competencies to adapt to environmental dynamics. Meanwhile, the NRBV enriches this perspective by positioning sustainability-oriented resources and capabilities as critical drivers of long-term competitiveness [49,50,51,52].

3. METODOLOGI

This article employs a quantitative approach through survey analysis to examine the relationships among variables, followed by a qualitative phase using in-depth interviews to explore the underlying mechanisms and contextual dynamics of these relationships. The research population consists of 285 palm oil mills (POMs) operating in Riau Province. A total of 74 respondents were selected using purposive sampling based on the following criteria: (1) a minimum of five years of experience in the palm oil industry, (2) involvement in operational decision-making processes, and (3) representation across different partnership models. The sample composition comprises 44 respondents (59.5%) from the Kredit Koperasi Primer Anggota (KKPA) partnership model and 30 respondents (40.5%) representing independent smallholders. Primary data were collected using a structured questionnaire adapted from previously validated instruments [32,53]. The questionnaire employed a five-point Likert scale and consisted of 39 indicators distributed across four latent constructs. In addition, qualitative data were obtained through in-depth interviews with 15 key informants selected through expert judgment, aimed at complementing and contextualizing the quantitative findings. Quantitative data analysis was conducted using Partial Least Squares–Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) with SmartPLS [53,54]. The model evaluation followed a two-step procedure comprising the outer model assessment (validity and reliability testing) and the inner model assessment (hypothesis testing and structural path analysis). To triangulate and enrich the results, the qualitative data were analyzed using thematic analysis, allowing for the identification of patterns and themes that supported the quantitative outcomes.

The validity and reliability of the research instrument were tested using the PLS-SEM approach in accordance with the guidelines established by Hair et al. (2022) for evaluating reflective measurement models [53,54]. The measurement model consisted of 39 indicators categorized into four latent constructs: Lean Management (12 indicators), Eco-Innovation (15 indicators), Organizational Agility (6 indicators), and Sustainable Operational Excellence (6 indicators). Each construct was assessed for convergent validity, discriminant validity, and composite reliability to ensure robustness and consistency of the measurement framework.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Results

The validity and reliability of the research instrument were examined using the Partial Least Squares-Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) approach with SmartPLS software, following the guidelines established by Hair et al. (2022) for reflective measurement model evaluation [53][54]. The measurement model comprised 39 indicators distributed across four latent constructs, Lean Management (12 indicators), Eco-Innovation (15 indicators), Organizational Agility (6 indicators), and Sustainable Operational Excellence (6 indicators). All indicators were designed in a reflective format, grounded in the Natural Resource-Based View (NRBV) theory, which emphasizes that organizational capabilities are reflected through a combination of tangible and intangible resources that are valuable, rare, inimitable, and organized [16][19]. The results of the convergent validity analysis indicated that the Average

Variance Extracted (AVE) values for all constructs exceeded the recommended threshold of 0.50, with Lean Management reaching 0.587, Eco-Innovation 0.612, Organizational Agility 0.569, and Sustainable Operational Excellence 0.634.

Composite reliability values ranged from 0.821 to 0.894, demonstrating strong internal consistency and meeting the criteria established by Fornell and Larcker (1981) for a robust measurement model. Discriminant validity was confirmed using both the Fornell-Larcker criterion and cross-loading analysis, which verified that each construct possessed distinct conceptual characteristics that could be statistically differentiated.

Table 1: Path Coefficients and Significance of Direct Relationships

Path Relationship	Path Coefficient (β)	Standard Deviation	T-Statistics	P-Value
LM \rightarrow EI	0.768	0.038	20.233	0.000
LM \rightarrow OA	0.212	0.104	2.031	0.042
LM \rightarrow SOE	0.258	0.114	2.255	0.024
EI \rightarrow OA	0.651	0.102	6.362	0.000
EI \rightarrow SOE	0.632	0.132	4.790	0.000

Notes: LM: Lean Management; EI: Eco-Innovation; OA: Organizational Agility; SOE: Sustainable Operational Excellence

The outer loading evaluation revealed that most indicators achieved loading values above 0.70. However, several indicators within the Green Technology dimension of the Eco-Innovation construct exhibited slightly lower loadings (ranging from 0.65 to 0.69). This finding aligns with the qualitative interview data, which indicated that the implementation of environmentally friendly technologies remains in the developmental phase for most palm oil mills in Riau Province, particularly in relation to ongoing research and development initiatives concerning the use of organic fertilizers, which are still under experimentation and improvement. The path coefficient results revealed an intriguing pattern of relationships, with varying strengths across the structural paths. The relationship between Lean Management and Eco-Innovation exhibited the strongest path coefficient of 0.768 with a *t*-statistic of 20.233 ($p < 0.001$), indicating a highly significant and substantial influence. This finding aligns with the results of the in-depth interviews, which emphasized that lean management practices, particularly those related to top management leadership and operational cost efficiency, serve as the foundation for developing environmentally friendly innovations. Respondents from the KKPA model reported that a well-understood corporate vision, mission, and goals among employees and cooperatives (KUD) have encouraged the implementation of standardized production processes that are not only efficient but also environmentally sustainable. This supports the propositions of Lean Management Theory as articulated by Hernandez-Matias et al. (2020) [32]. The influence of Eco-Innovation on Sustainable Operational Excellence demonstrated a path coefficient of 0.632 with a *t*-statistic of 4.790 ($p < 0.001$), confirming the hypothesis that ecology-based innovation acts as a primary driver in achieving sustainable operational excellence. This result is consistent with the findings of Fernando et al. (2021) in the automotive industry [28]. Field data corroborated this outcome, showing that palm oil mills (PKS) implementing RSPO (Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil) and ISPO (Indonesian Sustainable Palm Oil) audits

consistently exhibit stronger performance in economic and social sustainability dimensions, although challenges remain in achieving full environmental sustainability. The interview data further confirmed that cross-functional coordination, facilitated through regular forums with smallholder farmers and open dialogues with NGOs and local stakeholder organizations, has enhanced the organizations' eco-innovation capabilities.

The relationship between Eco-Innovation and Organizational Agility yielded a path coefficient of 0.651 with a *t*-statistic of 6.362 ($p < 0.001$), indicating that the development of eco-friendly innovation simultaneously strengthens an organization's ability to adapt to external changes. This finding is consistent with Dynamic Capabilities Theory as developed by Carvalho et al. (2019), which posits that innovation capabilities serve as antecedents of organizational agility [20][22]. However, a surprising finding emerged: Organizational Agility did not have a significant effect on Sustainable Operational Excellence, with a path coefficient of -0.028 and a *t*-statistic of 0.213 ($p = 0.831$). This result contradicts the initial hypothesis and offers new insight into the mechanisms underlying the achievement of SOE in Indonesia's traditional palm oil industry, characterized by long production cycles and relatively stable market structures.

Fig 1: Output SEM-PLS

The mediation analysis employed a serial mediation approach to explore the indirect pathways through which Lean Management influences Sustainable Operational Excellence (SOE) via Eco-Innovation and Organizational Agility, adopting the multiple mediator methodology proposed by Hayes (2017). The results revealed a complex mediation pattern that only partially aligned with the initial theoretical assumptions. The single mediation path of Lean Management → Eco-Innovation → Sustainable Operational Excellence demonstrated a significant indirect effect of 0.485 with a *t*-statistic of 4.658 ($p < 0.001$), indicating a robust mediating role of Eco-Innovation. This finding suggests that approximately 65.3% of the total effect of Lean Management on SOE is transmitted through Eco-Innovation, while the remaining 34.7% represents a direct effect, consistent with the concept of partial mediation established in the SEM literature [53][54]. Insights from the in-depth interviews provided a contextual explanation for this result. The implementation of lean principles, such as cost efficiency through cooperative-based management systems (KUD) and the 5% management fee mechanism, has stimulated cross-functional coordination and compliance with environmental regulations. Field observations further revealed that palm oil mills (PKS) applying standardized fruit sorting, direct labor allocation in plantation areas under HGU ownership, and R&D collaboration with agricultural laboratories requiring at least 60% compliance with laboratory recommendations successfully integrated operational efficiency with sustainability practices.

The mediation path Lean Management → Eco-Innovation → Organizational Agility also demonstrated a significant indirect effect of 0.499 with a *t*-statistic of 6.421 ($p < 0.001$), confirming that Lean Management enhances organizational agility through the development of eco-innovation capabilities. This finding supports the theoretical propositions of the Dynamic Capabilities framework advanced by Motwani and Katatria (2024) [23]. However, the full serial mediation pathway, Lean Management → Eco-Innovation → Organizational Agility → Sustainable Operational Excellence, was found to be statistically insignificant (indirect effect = -0.014 , $t = 0.201$, $p = 0.840$), indicating that Organizational Agility does not function as an effective mediator in the pathway toward SOE. This provides an important theoretical contribution to understanding the mechanisms underpinning sustainable operational excellence in traditional industries. Qualitative evidence from the interviews suggests that the concept of organizational agility, which emphasizes rapid responsiveness and flexibility in dynamic markets, may be less applicable within the palm oil sector, which is characterized by long production cycles (25–30 years) and relatively stable market structures. Respondents indicated that decision-making flexibility and problem-solving in production processes tend to be reactive rather than proactive, thus offering limited contribution to long-term operational sustainability.

4.2 Discussion

The structural model revealed varying levels of significance across the hypothesized relationships, offering substantive contributions to the body of knowledge on sustainable operations management. Hypothesis H1, which posited a positive relationship between Lean Management and Eco-Innovation, was strongly supported ($\beta = 0.768$, $p < 0.001$). This finding

aligns with the Natural Resource-Based View (NRBV), which asserts that operational efficiency serves as the foundation for developing innovative capabilities [16][19]. The implementation of lean management principles, particularly those related to top management leadership and cross-functional teamwork, has been instrumental in establishing a solid foundation for fostering regular discussion forums with farmers and ensuring compliance with RSPO and ISPO sustainability standards. These findings corroborate the results of Almeida and Wasim (2023), who identified lean practices as key enablers of eco-innovation within SMEs [30].

Hypotheses H2 and H3, concerning the direct influence of Lean Management on Organizational Agility ($\beta = 0.212, p = 0.042$) and Sustainable Operational Excellence ($\beta = 0.258, p = 0.024$), were also supported, although with moderate effect sizes. These results confirm that lean principles not only exert indirect effects through mediating variables but also have a direct influence on organizational outcomes, reinforcing the propositions of Hernandez-Matias et al. (2020) regarding the multidimensional impacts of lean manufacturing practices [32]. Field evidence indicated that initiatives such as standardized fruit sorting, direct labor deployment on plantation lands under HGU ownership, and R&D collaborations with agricultural laboratories have directly enhanced organizational responsiveness and operational sustainability. Furthermore, the integration of internal audits with KUD cooperatives and external audits coordinated with the Plantation Office strengthened the direct pathway from lean practices to operational excellence.

Table 2: Path Coefficients and Significance of Direct Relationships

Mediation Path	Original Sample	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation	T-Statistics	P-Value	Status
LM → EI → OA	0.499	0.516	0.078	6.421	0.000	Significant
LM → EI → SOE	0.485	0.510	0.104	4.658	0.000	Significant
EI → OA → SOE	-0.018	-0.024	0.089	0.205	0.837	Not Significant
LM → EI → OA → SOE	-0.014	-0.018	0.069	0.201	0.840	Not Significant
LM → OA → SOE	-0.006	-0.008	0.031	0.194	0.846	Not Significant

Notes: LM: Lean Management; EI: Eco-Innovation; OA: Organizational Agility; SOE: Sustainable Operational Excellence

Hypothesis H4, which examined the relationship between Eco-Innovation and Organizational Agility, was strongly supported ($\beta = 0.651, p < 0.001$). This finding indicates that the development of environmentally oriented innovation capabilities simultaneously enhances an organization's adaptability to external dynamics. In-depth interviews revealed that palm oil mills (PKS) implementing internal and external audits as well as cross-functional coordination demonstrated superior decision-making agility in addressing production challenges and responding to regulatory changes. This supports the Dynamic Capabilities framework articulated by Carvalho et al. (2021), which emphasizes innovation capabilities as critical building blocks for organizational agility [22]. Hypothesis H5, testing the influence of Eco-Innovation on Sustainable Operational Excellence, was also significantly supported ($\beta = 0.632, p < 0.001$), consistent with the theoretical view that green innovation acts as a primary driver

of sustainability performance, as suggested by Pinzón-Castro et al. (2024) and Fernando et al. (2021) [27][28]. Conversely, Hypothesis H6, which proposed a positive relationship between Organizational Agility and Sustainable Operational Excellence, was rejected ($\beta = -0.028$, $p = 0.831$). This result offers new theoretical insights into the limitations of agility concepts in industries characterized by long production cycles, such as palm oil. The finding challenges the assumptions of Organizational Agility Theory advanced by Zighan and Dwaikat (2023), which posit the universal applicability of agility across industries [25]. In the context of the palm oil sector in Riau Province, responsiveness may be less relevant than consistency and long-term stability, given production cycles lasting 25–30 years and a relatively predictable market structure.

The article offers several actionable managerial implications for palm oil mills (PKS) in Riau Province, focusing on the development of capabilities that yield the most substantial returns in achieving Sustainable Operational Excellence. First, prioritizing investment in Eco-Innovation capabilities, particularly in Green Technology and Market Focus, can provide optimal returns in enhancing SOE. Field data indicated that mills engaged in R&D on organic fertilizers, though still in early stages, are progressing toward stronger environmental sustainability. Regular environmental and waste audits conducted every three months should be complemented by the adoption of more advanced technologies, following the best practices in lean eco-efficient innovation highlighted by Ball and Lunt (2020) [26][31]. Second, the KKPA partnership model should be promoted as a best-practice framework for replication across other regions of Riau, given its superior performance across all SOE dimensions. The balanced core–plasma partnership structure, effective communication forums, and comprehensive audit systems have proven more effective than independent farmer models. However, the implementation of such models requires strong institutional support and capacity-building initiatives, particularly in cooperative management and financial literacy. The Provincial Government of Riau could facilitate this transformation by developing policy frameworks that promote the transition from independent to KKPA models through technical assistance and financial incentives, aligning with the recommendations of Henríquez-Machado et al. (2021) on achieving sustainability through operational excellence in emerging economies [15].

Third, strengthening cross-functional coordination and regulatory compliance can provide significant leverage in achieving multiple performance outcomes, given the central mediating role of Eco-Innovation within the model. Empirical evidence revealed that routine discussion forums with farmers and open consultations with NGOs or social organizations not only enhance eco-innovation but also simultaneously reinforce organizational agility. Investments in communication infrastructure and stakeholder engagement mechanisms can therefore generate substantial multiplier effects. PKS managers should adopt a systematic approach to supplier involvement, particularly for fertilizer suppliers meeting required quality standards, while strengthening compliance with international certifications such as RSPO and ISPO to gain access to premium markets. This supports the proposition of Fernando et al. (2024) regarding the integration of sustainable supply chain practices as a foundation for sustainable operational excellence [19,55].

5. CONCLUSION

This article developed and empirically validated an integrated *Green Lean-Agile Management* (GLAM) framework to ensure the long-term sustainability of operational excellence initiatives in the crude palm oil industry of Riau Province, Indonesia. The findings confirm that *Lean Management* plays a pivotal role in fostering *Eco-Innovation*, which subsequently enhances both *Organizational Agility* and *Sustainable Operational Excellence* (SOE). Among the observed pathways, *Eco-Innovation* emerged as the most influential mediator, explaining over 65% of the total effect of Lean Management on SOE. This supports the core assumptions of the *Natural Resource-Based View* (NRBV) and *Dynamic Capabilities Theory*, emphasizing that operational efficiency and innovation capabilities collectively drive long-term sustainability outcomes. Conversely, *Organizational Agility* did not exhibit a significant direct influence on SOE, suggesting that responsiveness and flexibility, while essential in volatile industries, may hold limited strategic importance in traditional agro-industrial sectors characterized by long production cycles and relatively stable market dynamics. This insight challenges the universal applicability of agility-based frameworks and highlights the need for contextual adaptation when applying modern management concepts to mature and resource-intensive industries such as palm oil. Overall, the results extend theoretical understanding by establishing *Eco-Innovation* as a critical mechanism linking lean operational practices to sustainable organizational performance. From a practical perspective, this article proposes three strategic directions to advance sustainability-driven operational excellence in the palm oil industry. First, developing *eco-innovation capability* should be a top priority. Palm oil mills should invest in green technology adoption, organic fertilizer R&D, and regulatory compliance systems such as RSPO and ISPO audits. These initiatives will enhance environmental performance while maintaining operational efficiency, ensuring alignment with international sustainability standards.

Second, the institutionalization of collaborative partnership models is essential. The KKPA cooperative scheme demonstrated superior sustainability outcomes compared to independent smallholders. Replicating this model across Riau Province, with institutional backing, capacity-building programs, and financial literacy initiatives, can accelerate the diffusion of sustainable practices and promote socio-economic equity within the sector.

Third, strengthening cross-functional coordination and compliance mechanisms is vital for sustaining long-term excellence. Establishing regular multi-stakeholder forums that involve farmers, local governments, and NGOs can foster transparency, stimulate innovation, and improve responsiveness to sustainability challenges. Building robust communication infrastructures and supplier engagement systems will further enhance the mediating role of *eco-innovation* in achieving *sustainable operational excellence*.

Finally, this article recommends that future research adopt longitudinal and cross-regional designs to capture the dynamic evolution of sustainability transformations over time. Incorporating digital transformation variables, such as Industry 4.0 adoption, data-driven decision-making, and environmental performance analytics, could further enrich the GLAM framework and expand its applicability to other resource-based industries.

References

- 1) B. P. P. Bappenas, "Rancangan Rencana Pembangunan Jangka Panjang Nasional (RPJPN) 2025-2045," *Bappenas. Jakarta*, 2023.
- 2) Badan Pusat Statistik Indonesia, "Statistik Indonesia 2025," Badan Pusat Statistik (BPS) Indonesia, Jakarta, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.bps.go.id/publication/2020/04/29/e9011b3155d45d70823c141f/statistik-indonesia-2020.html>
- 3) Direktorat Jenderal Perkebunan Kementerian Pertanian, *Buku Statistik Perkebunan 2023-2025 Jilid I*. Jakarta: Direktorat Jenderal Perkebunan Kementerian Pertanian, 2025.
- 4) Badan Pusat Statistik Provinsi Riau, *Provinsi riau Dalam Angka 2025*. Pekanbaru: Badan Pusat Statistik Provinsi Riau, 2025.
- 5) Dinas Perkebunan Provinsi Riau, *Buku Statistik Perkebunan Provinsi Riau Tahun 2024*. Pekanbaru: Dinas Perkebunan Provinsi Riau, 2024.
- 6) A. Pratiwi, "Peramalan Produksi Kelapa Sawit di Provinsi Riau Menggunakan Metode Pemulusan Eksponensial Ganda dari Brown." Universitas Negeri Padang, 2023.
- 7) Badan Pusat Statistik Provinsi Riau, *Statistik Kelapa Sawit Provinsi Riau 2023, Volume 4.*. Pekanbaru: Badan Pusat Statistik Provinsi Riau, 2023.
- 8) A. T. Wirawan, H. Ekwarso, and R. Y. Iyan, "Dampak Pandemi Covid-19 Terhadap Nilai Tukar Petani Di Provinsi Riau," *J. Econ. Media Komun. ISEI Riau*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 1–11, 2023.
- 9) A. P. Dewi, "Potensi Dan Pengembangan Ekonomi Industri Dalam Sektor Pertanian," *Perkemb. Ekon. Kreat. Ekon. Ind. Berbas. Digit.*, p. 185, 2023.
- 10) Z. Z. Parhas, "Peran Sensus Pertanian Dalam Mewujudkan Goals 2.4 SDGs," *Madani J. Ilm. Multidisiplin*, vol. 1, no. 11, 2023.
- 11) O. Briones et al., "Population dynamics of three cloud forest ferns of different growth form," *Plant Species Biol.*, vol. 38, no. 2, pp. 54–66, 2023.
- 12) F. Liu, J. Jiang, and S. Zhang, "Government Environmental Governance and Enterprise Coordinated Green Development under the Goal of 'Double Carbon,'" *J. Environ. Public Health*, vol. 2022, 2022, doi: 10.1155/2022/6605935.
- 13) M. R. Pangestu, "Politik Perdagangan Indonesia dalam Konteks Implementasi Asean China Free Trade Area (Acfta) Tahun 2015-2020." Universitas Islam Indonesia, 2023.
- 14) T. L. Kharlamova, A. V Kharlamov, and Y. A. Antokhina, "Effective management as a condition for innovative development of the national economy," *Eur. Proc. Soc. Behav. Sci.*, 2021.
- 15) H. Gamal, S. Albahri, H. Essa, M. Srivastava, N. Alghamdi, and W. Shaikh, "Driving Operational Excellence: Cost Savings and Performance Optimization through Tripping and Connection Time Optimization," in *International Petroleum Technology Conference, IPTC, 2024*, p. D021S077R002.
- 16) R. Henríquez-Machado, A. Muñoz-Villamizar, and J. Santos, "Sustainability through operational excellence: An emerging country perspective," *Sustainability*, vol. 13, no. 6, p. 3165, 2021.
- 17) W. F. H. Beeken, "A model for sustainable operational excellence through knowledge management practices and continuous improvement principles." 2009.
- 18) M. Sony, "Implementing sustainable operational excellence in organizations: An integrative viewpoint. *Production & Manufacturing Research*, 7 (1), 67-87." 2019.
- 19) Y. Fernando, F. Mergeresa, I. S. Wahyuni-TD, and N. S. Hazarasim, "Halal beauty supply chain and sustainable operational excellence: a moderator of the post-SARS-CoV-2 mitigation strategy," *J. Islam. Mark*, 2024.

- 20) A. M. Carvalho, P. Sampaio, E. Rebentisch, J. Á. Carvalho, and P. Saraiva, "Operational excellence, organisational culture and agility: the missing link?," *Total Qual. Manag. Bus. Excell.*, vol. 30, no. 13–14, pp. 1495–1514, 2019.
- 21) J. Antony et al., "An empirical study into the reasons for failure of sustaining operational excellence initiatives in organizations," *TQM J.*, vol. 35, no. 7, pp. 1569–1587, 2023.
- 22) A. M. Carvalho, P. Sampaio, E. Rebentisch, J. Á. Carvalho, and P. Saraiva, "The influence of operational excellence on the culture and agility of organizations: evidence from industry," *Int. J. Qual. Reliab. Manag.*, vol. 38, no. 7, pp. 1520–1549, 2021.
- 23) J. Motwani and A. Katatria, "Organization agility: a literature review and research agenda," *Int. J. Product. Perform. Manag.*, 2024.
- 24) A. Arshad, A. Ghaffar, M. U. Siddique, and S. Rehman, "Information Technology Adoption, Organization Performance and Organizational Agility: A Study of Small and Medium Enterprises," *J. Excell. Manag. Sci.*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 1–15, 2024.
- 25) S. M. Zighan and N. Y. Dwaikat, "Exploring organisational agility in SMEs," *Int. J. Entrep. Small Bus.*, vol. 49, no. 4, pp. 561–576, 2023.
- 26) P. Ball and P. Lunt, "Lean eco-efficient innovation in operations through the maintenance organisation," *Int. J. Prod. Econ.*, vol. 219, pp. 405–415, 2020.
- 27) S. Y. Pinzón-Castro, G. Maldonado-Guzmán, and R. J.-D. Toro, "Eco-innovation drivers really improve firm performance? Sustainable performance mediating role in Mexican automotive industry," *Int. J. Bus. Environ.*, vol. 15, no. 3/4, pp. 293–314, 2024.
- 28) Y. Fernando, M.-L. Tseng, R. Sroufe, A. Z. Abideen, M. S. Shaharudin, and R. Jose, "Eco-innovation impacts on recycled product performance and competitiveness: Malaysian automotive industry," *Sustain. Prod. Consum.*, vol. 28, pp. 1677–1686, 2021.
- 29) P. Ungureanu, C. Cochis, F. Bertolotti, E. Mattarelli, and A. C. Scapolan, "Multiplex boundary work in innovation projects: the role of collaborative spaces for cross-functional and open innovation," *Eur. J. Innov. Manag.*, vol. 24, no. 3, pp. 984–1010, 2021.
- 30) F. Almeida and J. Wasim, "Eco-innovation and sustainable business performance: perspectives of SMEs in Portugal and the UK," *Soc. Bus. Rev.*, vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 28–50, 2023.
- 31) S. Oduro, "Eco-innovation and SMEs' sustainable performance: a meta-analysis," *Eur. J. Innov. Manag.*, vol. 27, no. 9, pp. 248–279, 2024.
- 32) J. C. Hernandez-Matias, J. R. Ocampo, A. Hidalgo, and A. Vizan, "Lean manufacturing and operational performance: Interrelationships between human-related lean practices," *J. Manuf. Technol. Manag.*, vol. 31, no. 2, pp. 217–235, 2020.
- 33) S. Mahato, A. R. Dixit, R. Agrawal, J. Antony, J. A. Garza-Reyes, and A. Jamwal, "An empirical investigation on the deployment of operational excellence in SMEs," *Benchmarking An Int. J.*, 2023.
- 34) E. Turhan, I. Orhan, and A. Dalkiran, "Sustainable Operations for Airport Warehouse Cargo Management," in *International Symposium on Sustainable Aviation*, Springer, 2022, pp. 153–160.
- 35) S. Chakraborty, A. Sharma, and O. S. Vaidya, "Achieving sustainable operational excellence through IT implementation in Indian logistics sector: An analysis of barriers," *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.*, vol. 152, p. 104506, 2020.
- 36) Y. Kayikci, D. Durak Usar, and B. L. Aylak, "Using blockchain technology to drive operational excellence in perishable food supply chains during outbreaks," *Int. J. Logist. Manag.*, vol. 33, no. 3, pp. 836–876, 2022.
- 37) Sushil and P. Anbarasan, "Organization's sustainable operational complexity and strategic overview: TISM Approach and Asian Case Studies," *Sustainability*, vol. 13, no. 17, p. 9790, 2021.

- 38) S. M. Shemwell, "Attaining and Sustaining Operational Excellence: A Best Practice POC," in Proceedings of the International Petroleum and Petrochemical Technology Conference 2018 2, Springer, 2019, pp. 224–231.
- 39) M. Daoud et al., "ADCO Deploys the EFQM Excellence Model as a Management Framework for Sustaining Operational Excellence," in Abu Dhabi International Petroleum Exhibition and Conference, SPE, 2014, p. D031S043R006.
- 40) M. Ritz and T. Friedli, "Operational Excellence: The St. Gallen Model for Holistic Optimization," *Glob. Manuf. Manag. From Excell. Plants Towar. Netw. Optim.*, pp. 51–59, 2021.
- 41) K. Kareska, "Implementing KAIZEN for Continuous Improvement in Manufacturing Processes: A Quantitative Analysis of Efficiency and Productivity Gains," Available SSRN 4844986, 2024.
- 42) G. Deepti Raj, B. Prabadevi, and R. Gopal, "Evolution of Industry 4.0 and Its Fundamental Characteristics," in *Digital Transformation: Industry 4.0 to Society 5.0*, Springer, 2024, pp. 1–25.
- 43) S. Lopes, P. Leite, S. Carvalho, and P. Teixeira, "Using ITIL as part of the NIST Cybersecurity Framework," in 2024 12th International Symposium on Digital Forensics and Security (ISDFS), IEEE, 2024, pp. 1–6.
- 44) R. Sawhney, S. Treviño-Martinez, E. M. de Anda, G. L. Tortorella, and O. Pourkhalili, "A conceptual people-centric framework for sustainable operational excellence," *Open J. Bus. Manag.*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 1034–1058, 2020.
- 45) K. Ramdass, F. Nēmavhola, and K. Mokgohloa, "Leadership competencies for high performance-a quality system's perspective," *Int. J. Ind. Syst. Eng.*, vol. 38, no. 4, pp. 393–415, 2021.
- 46) J. Antony, "Six Sigma vs Lean: Some perspectives from leading academics and practitioners," *Int. J. Product. Perform. Manag.*, vol. 60, no. 2, pp. 185–190, 2011.
- 47) B. A. Lameijer, W. Pereira, and J. Antony, "The implementation of Lean Six Sigma for operational excellence in digital emerging technology companies," *J. Manuf. Technol. Manag.*, vol. 32, no. 9, pp. 260–284, 2021.
- 48) T. Guan and J. Delman, "Energy policy design and China's local climate governance: energy efficiency and renewable energy policies in Hangzhou*," *J. Chinese Gov.*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 68–90, 2017, doi: 10.1080/23812346.2017.1284430.
- 49) A. Chiarini and M. Kumar, "Lean Six Sigma and Industry 4.0 integration for Operational Excellence: evidence from Italian manufacturing companies," *Prod. Plan. Control*, vol. 32, no. 13, pp. 1084–1101, 2021.
- 50) M. I. Awwal, "Breaking the barrier of service hostility: A lean approach to achieve operational excellence," *Int. J. Bus. Econ. Res.*, vol. 3, no. 6–1, pp. 65–73, 2014.
- 51) A. Benkarim and D. Imbeau, "Organizational commitment and lean sustainability: Literature review and directions for future research," *Sustainability*, vol. 13, no. 6, p. 3357, 2021.
- 52) C. Tasdemir and R. Gazo, "A systematic literature review for better understanding of lean driven sustainability," *Sustainability*, vol. 10, no. 7, p. 2544, 2018.
- 53) J. J. F. Hair, G. T. M. Hult, C. M. Ringle, and M. Sarstedt, *A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM)-Third Edition*. 2022. doi: 10.1201/9781032725581-7.
- 54) F. Joseph, G. T. M. Hult, C. M. Ringle, and M. Sarstedt, *A primer on partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM)*. SAGE Publications, Incorporated, 2022.
- 55) M. Heriyanto, A. Fajri FEBRIAN, F. Karina ANDINI, T. Handoko, and D. Suryana, "Antecedents of Sustainable Competitive Advantages: A Case Study of Palm Oil Industries in Indonesia," *J. Asian Financ.*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 911–0921, 2021, doi: 10.13106/jafeb.2021.vol8.no2.0911.